

EOSC-Future

Improving and Integrating European Ocean Observing and Forecasting Systems for Sustainable use of the Ocean

Project Information

URL: www.eoscfuture.eu

Project Coordinator: ARC

Coordinator Country: Greece

Project duration: 01/04/2021 - 30/09/2023

Funding Programme - H2020-EU.1.4. - EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures

Project mission

The EU-funded EOSC Future project aims to integrate, consolidate and connect e-infrastructure, research communities and initiatives in Open Science to advance the EOSC platform of services (EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, Interoperability Framework). A major challenge in the project is to make a bridge between the e-infrastructure such as EGI, EUDAT, and GEANT, and the Research Infrastructures, organised in 5 science clusters. The project aims at onboarding of RI services into the EOSC marketplace in order to reach out to a larger audience of potential users, but also at Research Infrastructures adopting EOSC Core services in order to achieve more integration. For this purpose, there is a large workpackage in EOSC-FUTURE dedicated to so-called Cluster Science Projects, which target prototyping multidisciplinary services, led by RIs, and adopting several EOSC core services. These use cases aim to demonstrate that the potential of European research can be supported and accelerated by connecting the major stakeholders in the EOSC ecosystem, developing scientific use cases in collaboration with the thematic communities, engaging the broader EOSC community and increasing its visibility.

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities:

During the course of the project Blue-Cloud started a pro-active approach towards the EOSC community to increase awareness about the Blue-Cloud Open platform as a great example of implementation of the three main components of the EOSC Federation - EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and the Federation of Data & Data Services - into a unique Open Science platform accessible and usable by other research communities.

With the objective to showcase the project's unique approach to Data federation, valuable also for many other

thematic communities in the EOSC ecosystem, Blue-Cloud organised a workshop titled “Blue-Cloud Open Science platform as a model for a sustainable Data federation in EOSC” at the EOSC Symposium 2022, the main EOSC annual event that took place in Prague, Czech Republic, from 14th-17th November 2022 as part of the calendar of events of the Czech presidency of the Council of the EU. Details and outcomes of the event are collected in a [dedicated page on the Blue-Cloud website](#) and further reported in D5.4

In addition, as part of its dissemination activities, the EOSC Future project developed a series of EOSC in practice stories, to showcase use cases of EOSC tools or services, and share best practices for researchers, data experts and service providers in their daily jobs to inspire further uptake. Dick Schaap, Blue-Cloud technical coordinator and Pasquale Pagano, Blue-Cloud VRE Manager, were interviewed to showcase the technical impact of Blue-Cloud. As an outcome two EOSC in practice stories were prepared, one dedicated to the [Data Discovery and Access Service \(DD&AS\)](#) and one on the [Virtual Research Environment](#).

EOSC in practice story #11

EOSC Future

Keywords:
#service, #data, #access, #discovery, #infrastructure, #marine, #federation, #EOSCinPractice, #BlueEconomy

Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research

An EOSC in Practice Story where a common interface is provided for discovery and retrieval of marine data

The project involved

Blue-Cloud is the flagship initiative of the H2020 Future of the seas and oceans programme of the European Commission (Grant Agreement no 862409). The project delivers a collaborative virtual environment to enhance FAIR and Open Science in the marine domain. Started in October 2019, Blue-Cloud is deploying a cyber platform with smart federation of an unprecedented wealth of multidisciplinary data repositories, analytical tools, and computing facilities to explore and demonstrate the potential of cloud-based Open Science and address ocean sustainability, EU Green Deal, UN Ocean Decade, and G7 Future of the Oceans objectives.

The Challenge

There are several research infrastructures or other data services running in Europe that cover a multitude of marine-related sciences, providing specific datasets coming from observations collected with different methods. These infrastructures constitute a diverse world, each looking at a piece of the big picture. Blue-Cloud aims to overcome fragmentation and create a bridge between thematic science clusters – such as humanities, climate, food and agriculture sciences – and EOSC, creating a data federation and providing a common access to so-called thematic EOSC for marine data to enhance the visibility and discoverability of data from marine and environmental domains.

The Blue-Cloud Open platform is a great example of implementation of the three main components of the EOSC Federation – EOSC Core, EOSC Exchange and the Federation of Data & Data Services – into a unique Open Science platform accessible and usable by other research communities. Blue-Cloud is a front-runner of Data Federation in practice, giving its success in bringing together its data services covering 10M datasets from the marine domain and making them available via the DD&AS and the VRE to access, allowing interdisciplinary interactions between disciplines, thus demonstrating the value of bringing together a variety of providers and users within EOSC.

The solution – Data Discovery and Access Service

To overcome this fragmentation, a dedicated Data Discovery and Access Service has been implemented. This service facilitates discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products for external users in stand-alone mode, also interoperable with other Blue-Cloud services, such as the Virtual Research Environment. More than 10 million data sets are managed in blue data infrastructures (BDIs) that are connected to this Blue-Cloud service to serve federated discovery and access. A common interface is provided for discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products from each of the federated BDIs. The interface also includes facilities for mapping and viewing the locations of data sets, as this is part of the query dialogue. Moreover, the interface has a shopping mechanism, enabling users to compose and submit mixed shopping baskets with requests for data sets from multiple BDIs. The service is provided on a double level: at the first level, users can identify interesting data collections in an aggregated way in a common catalogue including entries from all the Federated BDIs. At the second level, users can get more specific and granular data.

The service provider

MARIS BV is a private company based in Noordoop (The Netherlands), specialised in developing web-based services and applications in the fields of oceanographic data management, geographical interfaces and websites with complex information ones.

The Users

Researchers in the marine environment can exploit Blue-Cloud services to find a broad variety of marine data and resources. More generally, researchers in other areas, such as environmental and social sciences, climate science, as well as business and industry players, can discover and use marine data for cross-domain research.

MARIS

EOSC in practice story #12

EOSC Future

Keywords:
#service, #environment, #demonstrator, #lab, #experiment, #computing, #data, #sharing, #processing, #analysis, #infrastructure, #marine

Providing computing platforms and analytical services to facilitate the collaboration between researchers

An EOSC in Practice Story where a common workspace is provided to researchers in the marine world to analyse, process, share data and co-develop research products

The project involved

Blue-Cloud is the flagship initiative of the H2020 Future of the seas and oceans programme of the European Commission (Grant Agreement no 862409). The project delivers a collaborative virtual environment to enhance FAIR and Open Science in the marine domain. Started in October 2019, Blue-Cloud is deploying a cyber platform with smart federation of an unprecedented wealth of multidisciplinary data repositories, analytical tools, and computing facilities to explore and demonstrate the potential of cloud-based Open Science and address ocean sustainability, EU Green Deal, UN Ocean Decade, and G7 Future of the Oceans objectives. In January 2026, a follow-up project, Blue-Cloud 2026, has been funded to further expand the ecosystem and the core services offered to researchers of oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters.

The Challenge

There are several research infrastructures or other data services running in Europe that cover a multitude of marine-related sciences, providing specific datasets coming from observations collected with different methods. These infrastructures constitute a diverse world, each looking at a piece of the big picture, sometimes hindering collaboration and data sharing. Blue-Cloud aims to overcome fragmentation and build a bridge between thematic science clusters – such as marine, climate, food and agriculture sciences – and EOSC, creating a data federation and providing a common access to a so-called thematic EOSC for marine data. By connecting leading marine data management infrastructures with horizontal e-infrastructure, the project aims to maximise the exploitation of data resources available from different sources. The Blue-Cloud framework consists of two major technical components:

- (1) a Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service, already presented in a previous EOSC in practice story, to serve Federated discovery and access to blue data infrastructures; and
- (2) a Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) to provide computing platforms and analytical services facilitating the collaboration between researchers, which is detailed hereafter.

The solution – Virtual Research Environment

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) facilitates collaborative research using a variety of data sets, analytical tools, and computing services that allow data access, processing, harmonisation, sharing, publishing, as well as the co-creation of new research products that can be stored in the same environment and shared with other users. Within the Blue-Cloud VRE, a set of analytical workflows facilitate the creation of shared workspaces that enable open science, relying on data sources and inputs that can be retrieved from the blue data infrastructures by means of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access; or can be retrieved from different other data portals and resources. The key value of the VRE is therefore to allow scientists and practitioners not only to easily access different sets of marine data but also to process and experiment with them via the analytical and visual tools made available by each demonstrator. The various VRE functionalities can be accessed logging into the Blue-Cloud Gateway via Single Sign On (SSO) and can be used in different ways based on the user needs.

For instance, if we consider data processing and analytics, users may exploit different types of support as shown in the examples below:

- Use of **standard technologies**, such as notebooks (The Blue-Cloud VRE has integrated JupyterHub) to create an environment and develop codes in any programming languages. The notebook is connected to the storage workspace of the infrastructure of the Blue-Cloud VRE and enables access to the data collected via the DD&AS. The notebook can be shared with other users to cooperate with collaborators

Pasquale Pagano, Senior Researcher at the InfraScience Laboratory @ Italian National Research Council (CNR)

EOSC in practice story featuring Blue-Cloud

Moreover, in a practical manner, exchanges were established between the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service respectively Blue-Cloud VRE Products Catalogue service with the EOSC marketplace, facilitating EOSC users to find and get interested in these Blue-Cloud resources, and then to navigate towards the Blue-Cloud for deeper and wider exploration and exploitation of these services.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/eosc-future